

Enhancing photoelectrochemical water oxidation using ferromagnetic materials and magnetic fields

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Abstract

Photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting provides a promising strategy for H₂ production. However, its performance is limited by severe carrier recombination and sluggish water oxidation kinetics. While numerous strategies, namely, elemental doping, morphology engineering, heterojunction formation and catalyst modification have been extensively explored to enhance the PEC performance, the application of external magnetic fields to affect the catalysis or charge carrier dynamics remains yet to be exploited. Herein, BiVO₄, is first selected as a representative photoanode, demonstrating that an ultrathin ferromagnetic coating based on Fe₂TiO₅, when combined with an external magnetic field, boosts its solar water oxidation performance. The combined analyses of the charge transfer and separation efficiency together with ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy and transient absorption spectroscopy data revealed that the magnetic field positively affect the band alignment across the BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ interface improving the charge separation, while the oxygen evolution at the Fe₂TiO₅/electrolyte interface was promoted. Finally, we expand this concept to other metal oxide photoanodes, such as TiO₂, WO₃ and Fe₂O₃, demonstrating the universality of such approach. Overall, this work pioneers a novel route to harvest external magnetic fields and improve the PEC response of common non-magnetic semiconductor photoelectrodes in photoelectrocatalytic conversion.

Introduction

Photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting emerged as a promising strategy for converting sunlight into hydrogen.¹⁻⁷ One of the major bottlenecks encountered in achieving high-performance PEC devices originates from the semiconductor photoanode and the high-energy demanding oxygen evolution reaction (OER). Over the past decade, several strategies have been explored to improve the photoanodes' activity towards the OER, namely, elemental doping,⁸⁻⁹ morphology control,¹⁰ heterojunction construction,¹¹⁻¹² coupling catalysts,¹³⁻¹⁴ etc. However, despite these efforts, the overall efficiency of the device remains insufficient for practical applications, and therefore, new strategies to manipulate the photogenerated charge carrier dynamics and improve the interfacial charge transfer are demanded.

Interestingly, in electrocatalytic systems for OER, the application of external magnetic fields (MF) was demonstrated to boost the performance. For example, Xu et al. reported that using ferromagnetic ordered CoFe_2O_4 catalysts as spin polarizers enhanced the OER under a constant MF.¹⁵ Liu et al. demonstrated a spin-dependent reaction pathway using spin-rearranged $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.2}$ MOF, resulting in excellent electrocatalytic OER activity due to spin-correlated catalytic activity.¹⁶ Likewise, Xu et al. revealed that magnetizing a ferromagnetic material changed its magnetic domain structure, improving mass transport and accelerating reaction kinetics.¹⁷ Based on these encouraging results, although scarce, some authors have studied the impact of MF on the PEC performance of semiconductor photoelectrodes. Sang and coworkers demonstrated that applying a MF to the ferromagnetic ZnFe_2O_4 photoanode, accelerated its charge separation process. The authors argued that the external MF modulated the spin polarization, affecting the magnetoresistance and the recombination, resulting in an improved PEC performance.¹⁸ Likewise, Chen et al. demonstrated that the performance of FeCoSe_2 photoanodes is enhanced under an applied MF primarily due to the reduced charge recombination and the improved catalytic activity towards OER.¹⁹ To date, however, the use of MFs to enhance the performance of semiconductor photoelectrodes has been limited to ferromagnetic materials, drastically reducing the family of materials that could benefit from such an approach. Note, that some studies have reported improved PEC performance of non-magnetic photoelectrodes under applied magnetic fields.²⁰ However, physical phenomena related to the magnetohydrodynamics and the improved mass transfer in the electrolyte could be invoked to explain the improved performance in these cases, rather than any impact on the charge carrier dynamics or the catalysis at the photoelectrode. Therefore, enabling new strategies to leverage the benefits of MF in conventional semiconductor photoelectrodes is crucial to advancing the field of PEC water oxidation.

Inspired by these works, we propose a general strategy to improve PEC water oxidation performance of conventional non-magnetic photoelectrodes by coupling with a ferromagnetic material and applying an external MF. To make it work, the ferromagnetic materials should have a good band alignment with the photoelectrode

materials and should exhibit a positive effect under the magnetic stimulus. Herein, we first select BiVO_4 as a representative photoanode to demonstrate the concept by coating it with Fe_2TiO_5 . The composite $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoelectrode shows enhanced PEC water oxidation performance due to the formation of heterojunction and improved catalytic activity. Additionally, applying an external MF further improves its PEC response from 3.06 mA/cm^2 to 3.33 mA/cm^2 at 1.23 V vs RHE. A comprehensive analysis revealed that the MF not only improved the catalytic response but also the charge separation, by promoting the spin polarization and the adjustment of the energy bands at the heterojunction, respectively. Furthermore, we extend this concept for other promising photoanodes, such as TiO_2 , WO_3 and Fe_2O_3 , showing its universality. Overall, this work pioneers a new strategy to “sensitize” conventional non-magnetic semiconductor materials to magnetic fields leveraging in such way their beneficial effects over the performance of PEC devices.

Results and discussion

Figure 1. Structural properties of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ thin film. **a** X-ray diffraction patterns of BiVO_4 , Fe_2TiO_5 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$. **b-e** High-resolution X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) of Bi 2p, V 2p, O 1s, Ti 2p and Fe 2p elements. **f** Top-view scanning electron microscopic (SEM) and **g** Cross-section SEM images of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode. **h** Spherical aberration correction high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) image, **i-m** High-angle annular dark-field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) image of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) elemental mapping images for Bi+Ti, Bi, Fe and Ti, respectively.

BiVO_4 was fabricated via a two-step method involving electrodeposition followed by annealing in air, whereas Fe_2TiO_5 was grown using a hydrothermal method followed by annealing. Detailed procedures are available in the supporting information. Fe_2TiO_5 is a chemically robust n-type narrow bandgap ferromagnetic photoanode, crystallizing in an orthorhombic structure (Figure S1).²¹⁻²³ X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of BiVO_4 , Fe_2TiO_5 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ thin films are shown in Figure 1a. Notably, the incorporation of Fe_2TiO_5 did not alter the XRD pattern of pristine BiVO_4 , likely due to the ultrathin nature of the coating. UV-Vis spectra of BiVO_4 and Fe_2TiO_5 thin films revealed absorption onset values ca. 500 nm and 580 nm, respectively (Figure S2), consistent with the reported band gaps of 2.5 and 2.17 eV.^{13, 22, 24-26} X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was utilized to analyze the chemical environment and the oxidation states in both pristine and Fe_2TiO_5 -coated BiVO_4 thin films. Notably, the Bi 4f and V 2p spectra exhibited a slight shift (0.15 eV) towards lower binding energies upon Fe_2TiO_5 coating (Figure 1b, c), indicating a strong interaction between BiVO_4 and Fe_2TiO_5 . The corresponding O 1s show drastic changes likely related to the fact that the oxygen environment on Fe_2TiO_5 and BiVO_4 are different (Figure 1d). Finally, the Fe 2p and Ti 2p XPS spectra corresponding to the heterostructure shown in Figure 1e, confirm the formation of the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ heterojunction. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed that pristine BiVO_4 thin films exhibited a worm-like morphology with an average thickness of ca. 1 μm (Figure S3), while Fe_2TiO_5 deposition increased the surface roughness (Figure 1f, g). Spherical aberration correction high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) imaging revealed an amorphous 4-nm-thick layer uniformly coating the surface of BiVO_4 , which was identified by the lattice spacing of 0.467 nm and 0.292 nm, characteristic of the (011) and (040) planes of monoclinic BiVO_4 (Figure 1h). Notably, high-angle annular dark-field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) mapping showed that Fe_2TiO_5 was homogeneously distributed over BiVO_4 particles (Figure 1i-m). Further analysis confirmed that the Fe:Ti atomic ratio was 1.58:0.85 (Figure S4), i.e., matching the nominal value of 2:1.

The energy level positions of BiVO_4 and Fe_2TiO_5 were estimated using ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS) measurements (Figure S2d). The schematic energy band structure of BiVO_4 and Fe_2TiO_5 exhibits a staggered profile, i.e., a type-II heterojunction (Figure 2a), which is anticipated to effectively promote charge separation. The PEC response of both BiVO_4 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanodes were recorded under simulated (AM 1.5G) solar illumination. Figure 2b shows that the photocurrent recorded at 1.23 V vs RHE increased from 1.64 mA/cm^2 (BiVO_4) to 3.03 mA/cm^2 upon coating with Fe_2TiO_5 . In addition, a cathodic shift in the onset potential from 0.5 V_{RHE} to 0.35 V_{RHE} was detected. The incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) profiles correlate well with the absorption spectra. IPCE values for $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode are 50%~60% from 350 to 450 nm, ca. 30% higher than that of pristine BiVO_4 (Figure S5). The integrated photocurrents are 1.62 mA/cm^2 and 3.2 mA/cm^2 for BiVO_4 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$, respectively, consistent with the values obtained from the J - V curves (Figure S6).

Figure 2. Photoelectrochemical properties. **a** The calculated energy band structure of BiVO_4 and Fe_2TiO_5 , **b** J - V curves of BiVO_4 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode, **c** the charge separation efficiency (η_{sep} , right dashed line) and charge transfer efficiency (η_{trans} , left solid line) of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode, **d** the calculated ΔCPD of BiVO_4 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode. **e** Transient absorption decays of BiVO_4 (blue) and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ (orange-red) under an applied bias of $1.2 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$. Decay traces probed at 700 nm after front-side laser excitation at 355 nm ($\sim 300 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, 1 Hz). Measurements were carried out in 1 M KBi buffer, $\text{pH } 9.5$.

To elucidate the impact of surface treatments on the bulk and surface properties, the charge separation (η_{sep}) and transfer efficiency (η_{trans}) were estimated (Figure S7a). The η_{sep} improved from 50.3% to 64.7% at 1.23 V vs RHE upon deposition of Fe_2TiO_5 (Figure 2c, dash line). This could be attributed to the improved charge separation resulting from the heterojunction formation. Notably, coating with Fe_2TiO_5 caused a significant increase in η_{trans} from 70% to 91% at 1.23 V vs RHE (solid line), attributed to the enhanced surface catalysis towards the OER. Previous studies have indicated that Fe_2TiO_5 acts as an efficient electrocatalyst, facilitating charge transfer to the electrolyte.²⁷⁻²⁹ Both, the improved η_{sep} and η_{trans} account for the enhanced photocurrent and earlier onset detected in Figure 2b. Dark J - V curves of BiVO_4 and Fe_2TiO_5 electrodes are displayed in Figure S8. Here, the onset potential of Fe_2TiO_5 shifted towards more negative potentials compared to BiVO_4 supporting the improved OER activity of the former.^{27, 30-31} Additionally, Kelvin probe force microscopy (KPFM) was employed to spatially resolve the potential distribution on the BiVO_4 electrode's surface (Figure S9), under both dark and light irradiation. The surface potential of all photoanodes decreased significantly under light irradiation, suggesting the accumulation of photogenerated holes on the surface. Moreover, the average surface photovoltage (ΔCPD , Figure 2d) of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ was approximately 65 mV higher than that of BiVO_4 , supporting the improved charge separation at the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ interface. Likewise, open-circuit potential (OCP) measurements showed that, under illumination, the OCP values shifted cathodically for the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode

(Figure S7b). This provided evidence of the mitigation of the intrinsic Fermi level pinning occurring on BiVO₄ when Fe₂TiO₅ is deposited. Note as well that the measured ΔOCP ($\Delta OCP = E_{OCP}^{dark} - E_{OCP}^{light}$) values for BiVO₄ and BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ photoanode were 143.3 mV and 204.6 mV, respectively (Figure S7c), indicating a more favorable driving force for PEC water oxidation.^{2, 26, 32} Notably, the OCP under illumination shifted to 278.1 mV for BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ photoanode, further supporting the role of Fe₂TiO₅ at promoting charge separation and facilitating efficient water oxidation.

Transient absorption spectroscopy (TAS) was employed to directly probe the population and lifetimes of photoinduced carriers in both bare and BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ photoanodes. Figure 2e shows the change in optical density (ΔOD) of BiVO₄ and BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ upon excitation over a μ s-s timescale at an applied bias of +1.2 V vs RHE (see Figure S11 for measurements as a function of the applied bias). Previous TAS studies have shown that photogenerated holes in BiVO₄ show a broad absorption feature peaking at 550 nm.³³ In this study, probe wavelengths of 700 and 650 nm were selected to investigate BiVO₄ hole populations, as the TAS spectra (Figure S10) obtained for these samples showed a flat absorption feature and these slightly longer wavelengths gave significantly improved signal-to-noise compared to 550 nm. The TAS decays in Figure 2e show clear biphasic behavior, with the decays at earlier timescales (μ s-ms) assigned to bulk recombination and with those at later timescales (ms-s) assigned to the competition between back-electron recombination and water oxidation.³⁴ Note that, as expected, these two decay regimes become more distinct at a higher anodic bias (Figure S11). The bare BiVO₄ and BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ films both showed increased hole-related signals under higher anodic bias (Figure S11a, b) due to the increased band bending, in agreement with previous studies on metal oxides, including BiVO₄.¹¹ It is worth highlighting that the Fe₂TiO₅ coating enhanced the magnitude of the ΔOD signal at all timescales, indicating a higher density of photogenerated holes. This confirms that the addition of Fe₂TiO₅ improves charge separation, and it is consistent with the formation of a type-II heterojunction.¹¹ The increased hole population is particularly significant on the timescales relevant to water oxidation and under higher applied bias (Figure S11c)

The magnetic properties of Fe₂TiO₅ powder were characterized by measuring the magnetization (M) as a function of magnetic field (H). Figure 3a portrays its room-temperature ferromagnetic behavior,³⁵ with the M-H curve exhibiting significant coercivity (-24.62 Oe) and remanence (2.54×10^{-4} emu/g) across the range from -400 Oe to 400 Oe. Further investigation of the Fe₂TiO₅ thin film using atomic force microscopy (AFM) did not show significant changes upon applying an external MF (Figure 3b, c top). However, magnetic force microscopy (MFM) evidenced clear alterations in the magnetic domain pattern after applying MF. Without MF, distinct magnetic domains (red and blue regions, Figure 3d) indicated well-separated magnetic phases (opposite polarity).¹⁷ With the MF, the magnetic domains of Fe₂TiO₅ aligned, transitioning into a nearly single-domain configuration (Figure 3e). This alignment

phenomenon further confirmed the ferromagnetic properties of the Fe_2TiO_5 thin film.

Figure 3. **a** M - H curves of Fe_2TiO_5 . Topographic (AFM, top) images of Fe_2TiO_5 films **b** unmagnetized and **c** magnetized under an out-of-plane magnetic field of 2000 Oe. Zero-field MFM phase (bottom) images of Fe_2TiO_5 films **d** unmagnetized and **e** magnetized under an out-of-plane magnetic field of 2000 Oe.

Next, the influence of the MF on the PEC performance of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ heterojunction was investigated, by including a magnet near the photoanode in a three-electrode configuration (Figure 4a, S15). The J - V curves depicted in Figure 4b and Figure S12 demonstrated that the performance of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanodes significantly improved under the influence of the MF, whereas that of pristine BiVO_4 barely changed. This corroborated the notion that the improved performance stems from the interaction of the Fe_2TiO_5 with the applied MF. At 1.23 V vs RHE, the photocurrent density increased from 3.06 mA/cm^2 to 3.33 mA/cm^2 with the incorporation of the MF. Moreover, increasing the MF intensity resulted in a proportional increase of the photocurrent at 1.23 V_{RHE} , highlighting, thus, the direct influence of the MF strength on the J - V response (Figure S13). Transient magnetic field-induced photocurrent (TMP) measurements (Figure 4c) further revealed that $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ exhibited an immediate positive response to the MF application (A-MF: applying MF, R-MF: removing MF), contributing to approximately a 7.3% increase in photocurrent at 1.23 V vs RHE. Note that the reflection of light at the magnet was ruled out to be contributing to the enhanced PEC response by using an anti-reflective coating (Figure S14).

Once established the positive effect of the MF on the PEC response, the η_{sep} and η_{trans} values together with fast-scan cyclic voltammetry were gathered to rationalize the role of the MF. η_{trans} to increase at potentials below 1.0 V vs RHE. This could be attributed to an improved surface passivation and catalytic activity triggered by the MF (Figure 4d). To explore the former phenomenon, fast-scan cyclic voltammetry experiments were performed (Figure S17). As observed, the cathodic peak located at around 1.5 V vs RHE, typically ascribed to the reduction of trapped holes at the interface and, therefore, to the surface states recombination (r-ss),³⁶⁻³⁷ decreased in the case of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ when the MF was incorporated. Quantitatively, the accumulated charge ($Q_{\text{r-ss}}$) was measured to be 0.015 C for BiVO_4 , 0.012 C for $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ and 0.01 C for $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ -MF (Figure S17c). The improved catalytic activity of the Fe_2TiO_5 towards the OER was evidenced by the earlier onset and reduced resistance for charge transfer exhibited by the Fe_2TiO_5 electrodes when

performing linear sweep voltammograms (Figure S8). Overall, this suggests that the application of MF effectively mitigates surface recombination processes and accelerates the OER, leading to improved charge separation and transfer dynamics and, therefore, enhanced PEC performance.

In addition, η_{sep} was further enhanced at high applied bias for BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ when the MF was incorporated, indicating that MF effectively promotes charge separation (Figure 4d). This improvement can be primarily attributed to two factors. Firstly, the decreased resistance of Fe₂TiO₅ under the external MF, as evidenced by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (Figure S8). While the resistance remained unchanged for BiVO₄ with/without MF, the charge transfer resistance significantly decreased for Fe₂TiO₅ with MF. The fact that the charge recombination is suppressed is also observed in other ferromagnetic semiconductors, analogous to the giant magnetoresistance effect.³⁸⁻³⁹ Secondly, the improved η_{sep} may result from the change in the band alignment. After applying the MF, the Fermi level of Fe₂TiO₅ was found to shift upwards by UPS analysis (Figure S18), in agreement with the shift of the flat band detected by means of the Mott-Schottky plot (Figure S19). This reinforces the notion that the built-in electric field is strengthened under the MF, resulting in a larger photovoltage. This is further supported by the enhanced photocurrent recorded in the presence of a sacrificial hole scavenger (Figure S12c). However, to the best of our knowledge, there is currently no theoretical explanation for the MF-induced shift of the Fermi level. In non-magnetic semiconductors, the density of states is evenly distributed between spin-up and spin-down states, whereas in ferromagnetic semiconductors, one spin direction is favored due to alignment with the magnetization, leading to an “exchange splitting energy” between majority and minority spin states (Figure 5a, b).^{18, 40} Bearing this in mind, we hypothesize that after the magnetization of Fe₂TiO₅ the distribution of density of states (DOS) for spin-up and -down electrons changed, therefore altering the resulting Fermi level. The resulting preferential spin polarization of holes within the more uniform and larger ferromagnetic domains could preferentially favor the occurrence of the OER via the triplet O₂,⁴¹⁻⁴² and therefore explain the improved catalytic response.

Figure 4e shows TAS measurements of BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ before and after exposure to an external MF. An increase in photocurrent density in BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ after exposure to a MF was correlated with an increase in hole population, particularly at earlier timescales. This suggests that the magnetization process reduces bulk recombination and improves charge separation. This is in agreement with other characterization properties, including OCP (Figure S7, S16) and M-S spectra (Figure S19). Bias-dependent TAS measurements of both BiVO₄ and BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ with and without a MF are shown in Figure S21. The TAS decays of BiVO₄ remained unchanged after the addition of the external MF at all applied biases, while the BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ hole signals increased in the presence of the MF. This demonstrates the benefits of an external MF at enhancing the performance beyond the improvement triggered by the heterojunction formation. Furthermore, the fact that the same behavior is not observed in the bare

BiVO_4 highlighted the role of ferromagnetic-dependent spin polarization and the parallel arrangement of electron spin polarization at enhancing charge separation and transfer efficiency.

The PEC stability is recorded in Figure 4f and illustrates that the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ shows a 13% loss of photocurrent after 6 h. Characterization of the Fe_2TiO_5 -coated films after the stability test did not reveal changes in XRD, although slight morphological changes were observed (Figure S22, S24). These changes could be ascribed to the partial photocorrosion of the material under operation. Note that the incorporation of the MF drastically affects the stability. Indeed, the photocurrent density of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ under the MF decreased only 3% after 6 h of irradiation. SEM images and XPS spectra confirmed the excellent stability of the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode after testing with MF (Figure S24-26), suggesting that MF enhances stability by accelerating charge separation/extraction and mitigating charge recombination. Note that the XPS data evidenced slight shifts in the characteristic peak positions after PEC testing that do not support drastic changes in the composition or in the oxidation states of the elements.

Figure 4. **a** Schematic diagram of the experimental setup of the MF-enhanced PEC system. **b** J - V curves recorded for a $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode first in the absence and, second, in the presence of the MF, under AM 1.5 G illumination. **c** Transient magnetic response curves of a $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode recorded at 1.23 V vs RHE. **d** The η_{trans} (left solid line) and η_{sep} (right dashed line) values of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ with or without MF. **e** Transient absorption decays of a $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ recorded at an applied bias of 1.2 V_{RHE} , recorded before (orange) and after (purple) exposure to an external MF. For the magnetization process, the magnet was placed in front of the sample for 1.5 h and then removed before obtaining the second TAS trace. Decay traces probed at 650 nm after back-side laser excitation at 355 nm ($\sim 300 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, 1 Hz). Measurements were carried out in 1 M KBi buffer, pH 9.5. MF = magnetic field. **f** Stability test performed by recording the photocurrent at 1.23 V vs RHE of two different samples of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ one in the absence and another one in the presence of an external MF.

Collectively, these characterizations demonstrate that applying MFs to the BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ photoanode significantly enhanced the photocurrent (~10%) driven by three synergistic factors that improve PEC water oxidation performance (Figure 5a, b). (i) The fully aligned magnetic domain structure of Fe₂TiO₅ under MF facilitates spin-selective electron transfer, thereby improving the catalytic activity (Figure 3c); (ii) The upward shift of the conduction band edge (E_{CBE}) and valence band edge (E_{VBE}) of Fe₂TiO₅, strengthens the built-in electric field and the driving force for the hole transfer across the BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ interface, accelerating the charge separation (Figure S15); (iii) The reduced density of r-SS alleviates the trapping of photogenerated holes at surface recombination centers, promoting hole injection into the electrolyte for participation in the water oxidation reaction, as demonstrated by the decrease of Q_{r-SS} (Figure S17).

Figure 5. Energy level diagram of BiVO₄ and Fe₂TiO₅ portraying the alignment of the magnetic domains (1), the change in the energy of the conduction band edge (E_{CBE}) and of the valence band edge (E_{VBE}) (2), and the reduced density of r-SS (3) both in the absence (a) and in the presence (b) of an external MF. A scheme of the density of states (DOS) of both semiconductors as a function of the potential indicating the spin-up and spin-down contributions is included to portray the proposed hypothesis whereby the band shift observed on the Fe₂TiO₅ sample, under a MF, could originate from the changes in the DOS of the spin-up and -down. A cartoon depicting the alignment of the magnetic domains on the Fe₂TiO₅ is also included.

To illustrate the versatility of the strategy three common non-magnetic photoelectrodes, namely TiO₂, WO₃ and α -Fe₂O₃, were employed in conjunction with Fe₂TiO₅, and their corresponding PEC water oxidation activity was evaluated (Figure S27-S29). The PEC performance of these photoelectrodes with or without MF is shown in Figure S30. Notably, for the WO₃ photoanode, coating with Fe₂TiO₅ induced a cathodic shift in the onset potential from 0.8 V to 0.6 V vs RHE, and the photocurrent increased by approximately ~6% at 1.23 V vs RHE with magnetic stimulation (Figure S30a). Similarly,

the $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode showed a ~14% improvement in photocurrent under MF stimulation, with the onset potential shifting cathodically from 0.3 to 0.2 V vs RHE (Figure S30b). The enhanced photocurrent response under MF can be attributed to the favorable interface contact and appropriate energy band alignment between TiO_2 and Fe_2TiO_5 (Figure S31-S33). This trend is also observed in the PEC activity of the $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanode (Figure S30c). Furthermore, the larger built-in electric field between WO_3 , TiO_2 , and Fe_2TiO_5 enhances the driving force for accelerating carrier separation under MF conditions. Therefore, employing ferromagnetic semiconductors to modify non-magnetic photoelectrodes proves to be a viable strategy for enhancing PEC activity under MF stimulation.

Conclusion

In summary, our study proposes a versatile strategy to enhance PEC water oxidation activity using external MFs by combining conventional non-magnetic semiconductors (BiVO_4) with ferromagnetic overlayers (Fe_2TiO_5). Here, it was demonstrated that the presence of the MF improves the photocurrent density primarily owing to the alignment of the magnetic domains of the overlayer, which prompted the improved OER kinetics, the mitigation of the Fermi level pinning and specially, an enhanced photogenerated charge separation. Interestingly, it was found that ferromagnetic materials in the presence of MFs were able to induce drastic changes in the band bending of underlying non-magnetic materials, therefore, boosting the charge separation. Although the mechanism for this phenomenon remains speculative and demands further investigation. Understanding these intricacies of MF-induced enhancements is crucial for fully realizing their potential. Moreover, the use of magnetic stimulation not only provides new insights and impacts in the PEC field but also suggests potential applications and benefits across other related fields. Exploring MF effects opens exciting avenues for novel advancements and interdisciplinary collaborations aimed at leveraging magnetic properties for improved performance in various technological applications.

Supporting Information

Experimental section; Figures S1–S29 and Tables S1–S2 are included, along with additional interpretations of some results. Key contents include: Crystal structure of Fe_2TiO_5 (Figure S1), UV-vis adsorption spectra (Figures S2, S23–S25), XPS and UPS tests (Figures S2, S15, S22, S27), SEM, TEM, HRTEM, and EDX-line scanning images (Figures S3–S4, S19, S21, S23–S25, S29), IPCE curves (Figures S5–S6), LSV curves for BiVO_4 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanodes (Figures S7, S12–S13), OCP and EIS curves (Figures S7–S8), KPFM images of photoanodes (Figure S9), TAS curves for BiVO_4 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5$ photoanodes (Figures S10–S11, S17–S18), Fast-scan CV scans, Mott-Schottky curves, faradaic efficiency, and stability (Figures S14, S16, S20).

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Reference

1. Wang, Z.; Guo, Y.; Liu, M.; Liu, X.; Zhang, H.; Jiang, W.; Wang, P.; Zheng, Z.; Liu, Y.; Cheng, H.; Dai, Y.; Wang, Z.; Huang, B., Boosting H₂ Production from a BiVO₄ Photoelectrochemical Biomass Fuel Cell by the Construction of a Bridge for Charge and Energy Transfer. *Adv Mater* **2022**, e2201594.
2. Pan, J. B.; Wang, B. H.; Wang, J. B.; Ding, H. Z.; Zhou, W.; Liu, X.; Zhang, J. R.; Shen, S.; Guo, J. K.; Chen, L.; Au, C. T.; Jiang, L. L.; Yin, S. F., Activity and Stability Boosting of an Oxygen-Vacancy-Rich BiVO₄ Photoanode by NiFe-MOFs Thin Layer for Water Oxidation. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl* **2021**, *60* (3), 1433-1440.
3. Wang, S.; Liu, G.; Wang, L., Crystal Facet Engineering of Photoelectrodes for Photoelectrochemical Water Splitting. *Chem Rev* **2019**, *119* (8), 5192-5247.
4. Yang, W.; Prabhakar, R. R.; Tan, J.; Tilley, S. D.; Moon, J., Strategies for enhancing the photocurrent, photovoltage, and stability of photoelectrodes for photoelectrochemical water splitting. *Chem Soc Rev* **2019**, *48* (19), 4979-5015.
5. Pan, L.; Kim, J. H.; Mayer, M. T.; Son, M.-K.; Ummadisingu, A.; Lee, J. S.; Hagfeldt, A.; Luo, J.; Grätzel, M., Boosting the performance of Cu₂O photocathodes for unassisted solar water splitting devices. *Nature Catalysis* **2018**, *1* (6), 412-420.
6. Lee, D. K.; Choi, K.-S., Enhancing long-term photostability of BiVO₄ photoanodes for solar water splitting by tuning electrolyte composition. *Nature Energy* **2017**, *3* (1), 53-60.
7. He, B.; Cao, Y.; Lin, K.; Wu, M.; Zhu, Y.; Cui, X.; Hu, L.; Yang, Y.; Liu, X., Enhanced bulk and interfacial charge transfer in Fe:VOPO₄ modified Mo:BiVO₄ photoanodes for photoelectrochemical water splitting. *eScience* **2024**, 100242.
8. Wu, H.; Zhang, L.; Du, A.; Irani, R.; van de Krol, R.; Abdi, F. F.; Ng, Y. H., Low-bias photoelectrochemical water splitting via mediating trap states and small polaron hopping. *Nature Communications* **2022**, *13* (1), 6231-6243.
9. Shi, Y.; Yu, Y.; Yu, Y.; Huang, Y.; Zhao, B.; Zhang, B., Boosting Photoelectrochemical Water Oxidation Activity and Stability of Mo-Doped BiVO₄ through the Uniform Assembly Coating of

- NiFe–Phenolic Networks. *ACS Energy Letters* **2018**, *3* (7), 1648-1654.
10. Qiu, Y.; Liu, W.; Chen, W.; Chen, W.; Zhou, G.; Hsu, P.-C.; Zhang, R.; Liang, Z.; Fan, S.; Zhang, Y.; Cui, Y., Efficient solar-driven water splitting by nanoconeBiVO₄-perovskite tandem cells. *Science Advances* **2016**, *2* (6), e1501764.
 11. Selim, S.; Francàs, L.; García-Tecedor, M.; Corby, S.; Blackman, C.; Gimenez, S.; Durrant, J. R.; Kafizas, A., WO₃/BiVO₄: impact of charge separation at the timescale of water oxidation. *Chemical Science* **2019**, *10* (9), 2643-2652.
 12. Chang, X.; Wang, T.; Zhang, P.; Zhang, J.; Li, A.; Gong, J., Enhanced Surface Reaction Kinetics and Charge Separation of p-n Heterojunction Co₃O₄/BiVO₄ Photoanodes. *J Am Chem Soc* **2015**, *137* (26), 8356-8359.
 13. Zhang, X.; Zhai, P.; Zhang, Y.; Wu, Y.; Wang, C.; Ran, L.; Gao, J.; Li, Z.; Zhang, B.; Fan, Z.; Sun, L.; Hou, J., Engineering Single-Atomic Ni-N₄-O Sites on Semiconductor Photoanodes for High-Performance Photoelectrochemical Water Splitting. *J Am Chem Soc* **2021**, *143* (49), 20657-20669.
 14. Song, Y.; Zhang, X.; Zhang, Y.; Zhai, P.; Li, Z.; Jin, D.; Cao, J.; Wang, C.; Zhang, B.; Gao, J.; Sun, L.; Hou, J., Engineering MoO_x/MXene Hole Transfer Layers for Unexpected Boosting of Photoelectrochemical Water Oxidation. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl* **2022**, *61* (16), e202200946.
 15. Ren, X.; Wu, T.; Sun, Y.; Li, Y.; Xian, G.; Liu, X.; Shen, C.; Gracia, J.; Gao, H. J.; Yang, H.; Xu, Z. J., Spin-polarized oxygen evolution reaction under magnetic field. *Nat Commun* **2021**, *12* (1), 2608-2620.
 16. Zhou, G.; Wang, P.; Li, H.; Hu, B.; Sun, Y.; Huang, R.; Liu, L., Spin-state reconfiguration induced by alternating magnetic field for efficient oxygen evolution reaction. *Nat Commun* **2021**, *12* (1), 4827-4836.
 17. Ren, X.; Wu, T.; Gong, Z.; Pan, L.; Meng, J.; Yang, H.; Dagbjartsdottir, F. B.; Fisher, A.; Gao, H. J.; Xu, Z. J., The origin of magnetization-caused increment in water oxidation. *Nat Commun* **2023**, *14* (1), 2482-2490.
 18. Gao, W.; Peng, R.; Yang, Y.; Zhao, X.; Cui, C.; Su, X.; Qin, W.; Dai, Y.; Ma, Y.; Liu, H.; Sang, Y., Electron Spin Polarization-Enhanced Photoinduced Charge Separation in Ferromagnetic ZnFe₂O₄. *ACS Energy Lett* **2021**, *6*, 2129-2137.
 19. Fan, B.; Yu, Z.; Ding, L.; Jiang, R.; Hou, Y.; Li, S.; Chen, J., Magnetic field enhancement of the FeCoSe₂ photoanode for the oxygen evolution reaction by adjusting the hole density to reduce competitive adsorption between Fe and Co in a photoelectrochemical water-splitting system. *Catalysis Science & Technology* **2023**, *13* (15), 4451-4465.
 20. Yang, Q.; Du, J.; Nie, X.; Yang, D.; Bian, L.; Yang, L.; Dong, F.; He, H.; Zhou, Y.; Yang, H., Magnetic Field-Assisted Photoelectrochemical Water Splitting: The Photoelectrodes Have Weaker Nonradiative Recombination of Carrier. *ACS Catalysis* **2021**, *11* (3), 1242-1247.
 21. Li, H.; Yamahara, H.; Tabata, H., Epitaxial thin films of room-temperature ferromagnetic semiconductor based on Fe₂TiO₅-FeTi₂O₅ solid solution. *Applied Physics Letters* **2021**, *119* (2), 022402.
 22. Bassi, P. S.; Chiam, S. Y.; Gurudayal; Barber, J.; Wong, L. H., Hydrothermal Grown Nanoporous Iron Based Titanate, Fe₂TiO₅ for Light Driven Water Splitting. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2014**, *6*, 22490-22495.
 23. Melo, M. A.; Centurion, H. A.; Lucas, T. T. A.; Dereck N. F. Muche; Souza, F. L.; Gonçalves, R. V., Pseudobrookite Fe₂TiO₅ Nanoparticles Loaded with Earth-Abundant Nanosized NiO and

Co₃O₄ Cocatalysts for Photocatalytic O₂ Evolution via Solar Water Splitting. *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* **2020**, *3*, 9303–9317.

24. Liu, Q.; He, J.; Yao, T.; Sun, Z.; Cheng, W.; He, S.; Xie, Y.; Peng, Y.; Cheng, H.; Sun, Y.; Jiang, Y.; Hu, F.; Xie, Z.; Yan, W.; Pan, Z.; Wu, Z.; Wei, S., Aligned Fe₂TiO₅-containing nanotube arrays with low onset potential for visible-light water oxidation. *Nat Commun* **2014**, *5*, 5122-5129.

25. Luo, L.; Chen, W.; Xu, S. M.; Yang, J.; Li, M.; Zhou, H.; Xu, M.; Shao, M.; Kong, X.; Li, Z.; Duan, H., Selective Photoelectrocatalytic Glycerol Oxidation to Dihydroxyacetone via Enhanced Middle Hydroxyl Adsorption over a Bi₂O₃-Incorporated Catalyst. *J Am Chem Soc* **2022**, *144* (17), 7720-7730.

26. Wang, Q.; Wang, Z.; Liao, N.; Montilla-Verdú, S.; Contreras, M.; Guijarro, N.; Luo, J., Tailoring the Surface Termination of BiVO₄ Photoanodes Using Ammonium Metavanadate Enhances the Solar Water Oxidation Performance. *ACS Energy Letters* **2024**, *9* (7), 3308-3315.

27. Gao, Y.; Li, Y.; Yang, G.; Li, S.; Xiao, N.; Xu, B.; Liu, S.; Qiu, P.; Hao, S.; Ge, L., Fe₂TiO₅ as an Efficient Co-catalyst To Improve the Photoelectrochemical Water Splitting Performance of BiVO₄. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* **2018**, *10* (46), 39713-39722.

28. Sun, Q.; Qi, L., Triple-layer ITO/BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ heterojunction photoanode coated with iron silicate for highly efficient solar water splitting. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2021**, *426*, 131290.

29. Majumder, S.; Su, X.; Kim, K. H., Effective strategy of incorporating Co₃O₄ as a co-catalyst onto an innovative BiVO₄/Fe₂TiO₅ core-shell heterojunction for effective photoelectrochemical water-splitting application. *Surfaces and Interfaces* **2023**, *39*, 102936.

30. Du, H.; Guo, H.; Wang, K.; Du, X.; Beshiwork, B. A.; Sun, S.; Luo, Y.; Liu, Q.; Li, T.; Sun, X., Durable Electrocatalytic Reduction of Nitrate to Ammonia over Defective Pseudobrookite Fe₂TiO₅ Nanofibers with Abundant Oxygen Vacancies. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2022**, *62* (5), e202215782.

31. Mousavi, D.-S.; Asen, P.; Shahrokhian, S.; Irajizad, A., Three-dimensional hybrid of iron-titanium mixed oxide/nitrogen-doped graphene on Ni foam as a superior electrocatalyst for oxygen evolution reaction. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2020**, *563*, 241-251.

32. Wang, Q.; Wu, L.; Zhang, Z.; Cheng, J.; Chen, R.; Liu, Y.; Luo, J., Elucidating the Role of Hypophosphite Treatment in Enhancing the Performance of BiVO₄ Photoanode for Photoelectrochemical Water Oxidation. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* **2022**, *14*, 26642–26652.

33. Ma, Y.; Pendlebury, S. R.; Reynal, A.; Le Formal, F.; Durrant, J. R., Dynamics of photogenerated holes in undoped BiVO₄ photoanodes for solar water oxidation. *Chem. Sci.* **2014**, *5* (8), 2964-2973.

34. Le Formal, F.; Pendlebury, S. R.; Cornuz, M.; Tilley, S. D.; Gratzel, M.; Durrant, J. R., Back electron-hole recombination in hematite photoanodes for water splitting. *J Am Chem Soc* **2014**, *136* (6), 2564-2574.

35. Li, H.; Yamahara, H.; Tabata, H.; Seki, M., Epitaxial thin films of room-temperature ferromagnetic semiconductor based on Fe₂TiO₅–FeTi₂O₅ solid solution. *Applied Physics Letters* **2021**, *119* (2), 022402.

36. Chen, H.; Li, J.; Yang, W.; Balaghi, S. E.; Triana, C. A.; Mavrokefalos, C. K.; Patzke, G. R., The Role of Surface States on Reduced TiO₂@BiVO₄ Photoanodes: Enhanced Water Oxidation Performance through Improved Charge Transfer. *ACS Catalysis* **2021**, *11* (13), 7637-7646.

37. Shi, Q.; Murcia-López, S.; Tang, P.; Flox, C.; Morante, J. R.; Bian, Z.; Wang, H.; Andreu, T., Role of Tungsten Doping on the Surface States in BiVO₄ Photoanodes for Water Oxidation: Tuning the Electron Trapping Process. *ACS Catalysis* **2018**, *8* (4), 3331-3342.
38. Li, J.; Pei, Q.; Wang, R.; Zhou, Y.; Zhang, Z.; Cao, Q.; Wang, D.; Mi, W.; Du, Y., Enhanced Photocatalytic Performance through Magnetic Field Boosting Carrier Transport. *ACS Nano* **2018**, *12* (4), 3351-3359.
39. Baibich, M. N.; Broto, J. M.; Fert, A.; Nguyen Van Dau, F.; Petroff, F.; Etienne, P.; Creuzet, G.; Friederich, A.; Chazelas, J., Giant magnetoresistance of (001)Fe/(001)Cr magnetic superlattices. *Phys Rev Lett* **1988**, *61* (21), 2472-2475.
40. Lin, C.-C.; Liu, T.-R.; Lin, S.-R.; Boopathi, K. M.; Chiang, C.-H.; Tzeng, W.-Y.; Chien, W.-H. C.; Hsu, H.-S.; Luo, C.-W.; Tsai, H.-Y.; Chen, H.-A.; Kuo, P.-C.; Shiue, J.; Chiou, J.-W.; Pong, W.-F.; Chen, C.-C.; Chen, C.-W., Spin-Polarized Photocatalytic CO₂ Reduction of Mn-Doped Perovskite Nanoplates. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2022**, *144* (34), 15718-15726.
41. Torun, E.; Fang, C. M.; de Wijs, G. A.; de Groot, R. A., Role of Magnetism in Catalysis: RuO₂ (110) Surface. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2013**, *117* (12), 6353-6357.
42. Nazmutdinov, R. R.; Santos, E.; Schmickler, W., Spin effects in oxygen electrocatalysis: A discussion. *Electrochemistry Communications* **2013**, *33*, 14-17.